

The Importance of Understanding Applications and Strategies in Marketing MSME Products on Social Media during the Covid 19 Pandemic

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 12 November 2022	The purpose of this study was to find out how the techniques, elements, processes and activities of MSME actors in using digital marketing to compete during the pandemic. Research on digital marketing strategies for MSME to compete in this pandemic era uses a qualitative method with a descriptive analytical approach. Descriptive research is data collection based on factors that support the object of research. Qualitative research is concerned with the ideas, perceptions, opinions, beliefs of the people to be studied and all of them cannot be measured by numbers. The results of the study show that there are still at least MSME that use digital marketing (15.08%) as a strategy to increase sales and require an understanding of digital marketing. Based on research analysis, MSME that are already using digital marketing are able to survive and even increase sales without relying on conventional stores.
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INTRODUCTION

The global Covid-19 pandemic that has hit all countries in the world has affected all sectors of people's lives. In Indonesia, almost all sectors are affected, especially the economic ecosystem which has been the focus of society. Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic has caused a slowdown in the economic sector in Indonesia with its various derivatives. The Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector, which is part of the most important economic sectors, is feeling the impact. This has become a fear of all parties, because it has made the MSME sector experience a significant decline (Purga and Rijando 2021).

Several MSME actors experienced various problems such as: decreased sales, capital, distribution constraints, difficulty in raw materials, decreased production and the occurrence of many layoffs for workers and hunting which later became a threat to the national economy. MSMEs as the driving force of the domestic economy and absorbing middle-class workers face a decline in productivity which results in a decrease in important profits. Even based on a related Asian Development Bank (ADB) survey, the impact of the pandemic on MSMEs in Indonesia, 88% of micro businesses run out of cash or savings, and more than 60% of these micro and small businesses have reduced their workforce (Petri, 2020).

The Covid-19 pandemic has reduced the purchasing power of the public. Because people have reduced outdoor interactions to suppress the spread of the pandemic. So that many consumers move away and switch purchases digitally. The impact is that many MSMEs have to close their businesses due to declining purchases and still rely on sales outside the network (offline). Until some MSME sectors that have not adapted digitally are ultimately very affected by the closure of their outlets. Even so, the Covid-19 pandemic has indirectly prompted new changes in Indonesia's business style. This change is the transition from offline business to digital business which is also known as the phenomenon of digital entrepreneurship. Social media and market places (intermediaries) can be concepts to make it easier for MSME actors to get wider marketing access. (Mahanani, 2022).

All the MSME business actors in Indonesia have become the most important pillar for the economic ecosystem. Moreover, it is known that 99% of business actors in Indonesia are the MSME sector. The role of MSME has contributed 60% to the national gross domestic product and 97% of the workforce is affected by the pandemic. Meanwhile, only 16 percent of existing MSME have entered the digital economy ecosystem. In the context of Indonesia, the MSME sector is one of the main pillars of the fundamentals of the Indonesian economy. During the 1998 economic crisis, the MSME sector had a very positive

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contribution in saving the Indonesian economic ecosystem. The same thing happened during the Covid-19 pandemic, where the MSME sector has great potential to become an accelerator of national economic recovery (Nur & Wijayanti, 2020).

In increasing the results of MSME, an entrepreneurial model is needed that can adapt to technological advances. This is what gave birth to the digital entrepreneurship model. This business model comes from a combination of digital technology and entrepreneurship which then produces a new characteristic phenomenon in business dealings. In this case, the role of digital technology has a significant influence on the new business units created. New technology paradigms harness the potential for collaboration and collective intelligence to design and launch more robust and sustainable entrepreneurial initiatives. Even so, there are four dimensions related to digital entrepreneurship, namely digital actors (who), digital activities (what), digital motivation (why) and digital organizations (how).

According to records from the Ministry of Cooperatives and MSME, there are currently 10.25 million MSME stakeholders connected to digital platforms. In other words, there are already 16 percent or around 10.25 MSME that are connected to the digital ecosystem. That's because many MSME digitization programs will continue to be implemented by the Ministry of MSME and Cooperatives. It should be noted that the digitization program is part of the most important part of the transformation program of the Ministry of MSME and Cooperatives. In particular, consumer behavior has changed as a result of the global pandemic. The excessive trend of digitizing MSMEs has become a new habit for the community until the future (Hanim, Soponyono, & Maryanto, 2022).

The use of digital platforms decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic, MSME in Indonesia experienced a considerable increase. There are 42% of Indonesian MSMEs who already use social media. In other words: social media is a means to develop entrepreneurship and MSME sustainability. Meanwhile, based on data, McKinsey's e-commerce sales rose 26% with a total of 3.1 million transactions per day (Kompas.com, 2020). Even during the Covid-19 Pandemic, it has led to higher use of social media which of course correlates with an increase in sales transactions by MSMEs. In other words, MSME actors who have successfully completed Sales transactions during this pandemic are those who have successfully used digital platforms and social media (Andriyani & Aditya, 2021).

The development of digitalization of MSME will make the digital technology economy in Indonesia the largest in Southeast Asia by 2025. Even though MSME thus face three obstacles, namely; In the past, MSME were still constrained by the production capacity of goods. In fact,

many MSME fail in the digital market because they cannot meet the demands of the digital market. Second, the quality of resilience of MSME actors is not evenly distributed. Because players must be able to assert themselves in this digital market, large companies have also switched to using the platform during the Digital pandemic. Third, the formation of digital skills needs to be strengthened and strengthened Human Resources for MSME Business Actors. Because so far digital literacy and the quality of human resources for MSME actors are very minimal, so the impact is less than optimal in producing their respective superior products. In fact, the majority of MSME economic actors want to practice digital business in their business development (Surenggono, Erdiana, & Djamilah, 2021).

Efforts to develop digital MSME need synergy with internet users, who by the way are the millennial generation. These Internet users may be encouraged to join Digital MSME Development with reseller techniques. In this context, residents who can be invited to collaborate, especially the millennial generation and Generation Z are divided into several classifications, namely buzzers, influencers and trailers. More about the digital MSME development program is very dependent on government support, namely the ease of licensing. Therefore, connectivity is everything for better digital MSME to form (Mulyantomo, Sulistyawati, & Triyani, 2021).

The development of digital MSME is in line with the recently launched government program of the Ministry of Communication and Information (Kominform). Digital MSME training program. That's for no reason, because the various programs of this program aim to help MSME actors to be able to switch to digital platforms in business life. Because in 2021 the Coordinating Ministry for Maritime Affairs and Investment is expected to reach around 30 million MSME out of a total of 60 million MSME units that can enter the Digital ecosystem. According to current records, there are only around 11 to 12 million MSME selling on digital platforms, so there is still much to be encouraged. Start with digital sales on digital platforms (Supriyani & Untari, 2021).

Internet users in Indonesia reached 73% in 2008 November 2020, but the internet access gap is still quite large. This is something that the government must immediately resolve to support the MSME digitization program. The reason for improving digital infrastructure is the main key in developing MSME, along with the support of other programs, such as the Job Creation Law, which is seen as beneficial for MSME. The urgency of digital infrastructure in supporting the Proudly Made in Indonesia National Movement Program can encourage people to use it more in the future for local products (Novita & Yuliani, 2021).

According to the Minister of Cooperatives and MSME (Menkop UMKM) Teten Masduki, Indonesia's digital economy potential could reach IDR 1,800 trillion by 2025

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(Kumparan.com, 2020). Therefore, it is time for MSME actors to immediately adopt the use of digital in the development of their business units. That way, this huge market potential is not absorbed by third-party products (Kompas.com, 2020). There are three things that need to be considered for this by MSME actors when they want to enter the digital realm, namely; production quality, production capacity and digital competence. These three things must be emphasized by MSME actors not only opening business units in the complementary digital realm but tending to last a long time. Therefore, a digital development strategy is needed for MSMEs in the deployment of information technology infrastructure, production processes and market expansion in the short, medium and long term, so that small businesses and medium enterprises have competitiveness and can improve their performance (Raharja & Natari, 2021).

Digital payments have made Indonesia one of the largest and fastest digital network economies in ASEAN. It is important to use this potential of MSME to enable their business units to grow internationally. He also estimates the value of Indonesia's digital economy by 2025 to reach more than \$130 billion (CnnIndonesia.com, 2020). This great potential must be utilized by the government by trying to focus and expand access to digital markets to close the digital divide between regions, especially for micro-enterprises in different regions (Widayati & Augustinah, 2019).

The development of MSME digitization is not limited to digital marketing only. But also the introduction of digital payments in money is important. Therefore, this step can accommodate MSME actors in terms of digital debt settlement, which is always an obstacle. That way, this step will improve the quality of Indonesian MSME growing rapidly. So that is the end of the development of digital MSME, which will not only advance MSME in Indonesia at digital grassroots, but can last a long time in the digital market. Ending To return to this state, mitigation and recovery solutions are needed, through setting up demand-side drives and encouraging digital platforms to expand partnerships. In addition, cooperation in the use of innovation and technology is needed that can support improving the quality and competitiveness of product processing to marketing (Tabroni & Komarudin, 2021).

From this explanation, the researchers are interested in providing an understanding of applications and strategies in marketing MSME products on social media during the Covid-19 pandemic

METHODS

This study uses a qualitative method with a descriptive analysis approach, namely a qualitative approach to understand and describe the meaning of the rules of analysis included in the digital marketing strategy for MSME. Researchers use this method to emphasize an event or the

most important thing from a phenomenon in the form of an event or occurrence of the phenomenon being studied.

Qualitative details provide space for researchers to examine in detail descriptive research about the phenomenon under study, in order to obtain a policy for the implementation of actions or attitudes. Qualitative research looks at the real nature background, positions people as research actors, analyzes inductive information, which deals more with the process than the results of the study. The research was conducted and approved by the researcher and the research subject.

Qualitative analysis method is a research method that focuses more on aspects of a deep understanding of an activity rather than looking at the general research problem. This research method focuses more on qualitative descriptive analysis techniques, namely discussing problems in fact, because qualitative methodologies emphasize that the nature of one problem will be different from the nature of other problem cases. The aim of this research methodology is not generalization but a deeper understanding of the research being examined. Qualitative research serves as a category of content and hypotheses in qualitative research.

The qualitative descriptive approach method is a method of processing information through factor analysis related to the research subject by presenting more detailed information about the research topic. In general, researchers look for primary and secondary data sources to support the implementation of research. Primary sources were obtained through interviews with several MSME actors who have used digital marketing to market their products and were able to increase sales, while secondary sources you get from magazines, books, and literature studies on digital marketing of MSME.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The research that has been done states that digital marketing has a positive impact and results provide a significant contribution in improving the sales performance of MSME. As many as 70% of MSME players who use digital marketing stated that digital marketing will be the main strategy in marketing, while conventional stores will only be a complement. This happens because of the convenience and ability of digital marketing to reach more consumers (Syaifullah, et al., 2021).

This statement is also in accordance with research conducted by whoever says this MSME actors must be able to develop the courage to try new things, for example digital marketing to be able to further develop their business by creating social media accounts and regularly promoting or partnering with the market so that they feel confident. and increase creativity in product marketing. Accepting the use of the market as a means of selling MSME products is an effort to maintain or increase sales. This increase in sales is related

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to reducing operational costs with digital means. (Effendi, et al., 2020).

The use of social media as a starting point for digital marketing in product marketing must pay attention to regulations in marketing so that the results are maximum Attracting customers and transacting. The step to win the competition is through the implementation of targeted marketing strategies both in terms of quality, price and product competitiveness. Here are some digital marketing strategies that MSME can do using social media according to Some experts, namely:

1) Interesting and interactive content

a. Publish product photos and videos intensively on social media accounts. media algorithm Therefore, social media is to increase the traffic of high social media accounts Intensive publication of photos and videos of products helps unite MSME with their target customers on social media. the use of social media is also adjusted to the product segment itself (Ratih,et al., 2021).

b. Use Facebook Ads, Instagram Ads, YouTube Ads, Twitter Ads, Google AdSense, which can be easily accessed by MSME stakeholders through social media. The use of advertising (ads) on social media requires initial capital, but the benefits obtained are comparable and can even significantly exceed the capital used is problematic. This is because using advertising can reach consumers better based on the criteria we have previously set, based on age, place of origin, profession, gender, and even which accounts are usually seen by the target customer (Meileni,et al., 2021).

c. Create and publish marketing product videos, then stream them from social media accounts or run direct promotions of the products sold so that consumers can see them following the social media of MSME actors. This strategy when carried out correctly and consistently has a positive effect on ongoing businesses (Harianto & Sari, 2021).

d. Consumer involvement in the selection of products sold (type, color, model), Conduct intensive and effective training and introduction to business product quality on social media. In addition, the use of creative words, hypnotic writing (hypnowriting/copywriting) and using hashtags (#) that are appropriate to the product will make it easier for consumers to find products. This is how it forms brand awareness and can influence the purchase decisions consumers are looking for (Yuliastuti, et al., 2021).

2) Study Content Marketing Development

The growth of e-commerce is also very fast in Indonesia, making people's shopping patterns switch to electronic or online shopping, which creates new problems, the impact of this situation has caused the closure of retail stores in Indonesia to be widely used in recent years. Marketing content needs to be the focus of MSME stakeholders given the importance of content on social media,

search engines or markets. Many MSME actors still don't understand the importance of content marketing that underlies digital marketing. Content is the basis of the strategy and is very important to create brand awareness and increase social media traffic (Rosmadi, 2021).

3) Develop mobile marketing

Smartphone users are increasing day by day. This leads to content marketing. Mobile applications are a necessity which must then be developed by MSME actors who have many loyal customers. Marketing content from mobile applications is in the form of products, promotional information, or product purchase features that consumers are looking for. Because of this, MSME must gradually create or develop websites and blogs (Hadi & Zakiah, 2021).

4) Digital marketing integration.

Social media and the content served play an important role in search results. Google created with various purposes and benefits, one of which is to collect social signals through digital media. For this reason, MSME actors must ensure that any digital marketing can reach consumers simultaneously on various integrated social media channels so that marketing content can be distributed optimally (Purwasih et al., 2021).

The content of one social media with other social media has a relationship or uploads the same content, especially on Instagram, Facebook and Twitter in a format that is adapted to the social media used. Trusov in a journal written by Indika & Jovita said that electronic WOM and advertising through social media help marketing and attract consumers at a price. The content of a social media with other social media is related or uploaded the same content, especially on Instagram, Facebook and Twitter in a format the same is adjusted to the social media used. Trusov in the magazine by Indika & Jovita said that electronic WOM and social media advertising help market and attract consumers at cheaper and faster prices (Febriyantoro & Arisandi, 2018).

5) Sustainable Marketing The use of digital marketing can create sustainable marketing.

The reality is that everything is found online through social media, and searching through Google requires EO (Engine Optimization.) Creating content and marketing so that everything is integrated into sustainable marketing that continues to deliver results to MSME stakeholders (Winarti, 2021).

6) Personalized Marketing Effectiveness

This makes marketing in conventional media such as newspapers and television less effective, saturating media users. The information or content presented is not directly targeted to consumers who are looking for it. With personalized marketing on social media, e-commerce websites, email, and websites that adapt to advertising and consumer interest users, what happens when someone visits

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an online store?. With single and repeated visits, the website knows who the visitors are because there is already a previous track record (Tabroni & Komarudin, 2021).

Subsequent emails have been personalized and linked to products that have been used. Visit consumers when they shop online. The internet will capture consumer habits such as reading data from consumer browsing trails and then providing relevant useful information. This trend is driven by technology through the use of big data which is closely linked to digital marketing strategies to increase the marketing effectiveness of MSME actors. This is what MSME actors must explore in order to strengthen their position during the pandemic (Redjeki & Affandi, 2021).

7) Benefits of using digital marketing for MSME

Digital marketing strategy is considered to be a solution for MSME actors in transacting Competition during the pandemic, because digital marketing has several advantages according to (Joseph, Tulung, & Wangke, 2020), namely: (a) Being able to connect producers and consumers across cyberspace. Digital Marketing can connect without having to meet in person, even without having to know who to contact consumers. This is a digital record that stores consumer data that is still managed by MSME actors. (Novita & Yuliani, 2021); (b) Generate more sales using digital marketing minimizing distance and time constraints. No need to waste time. Consumers come to the store and can buy products with just their fingers. (Hidayati & Yansi, 2020); (c) Digital marketing is much more cost efficient than advertising in other media such as print, television or radio. With a more efficient cost, digital marketing is able to do more benefits than using advertising in other media. (Raharja & Natari, 2021); (d) Digital marketing allows sellers to serve their customers in real time. Connecting MSME stakeholders with consumers via smartphones anywhere at any time and everywhere. MSME do not have to stay in one place or stay in business to serve customers. (Joseph et al., 2020); (e) Generate profits whose face value is greater than the actual advertising costs incurred. This is one of the most important things that can be obtained from MSME actors with digital marketing. The use of advertising with a minimal price can generate many benefits (Redjeki & Affandi, 2021). (f) MSME help stabilize the brand position in the eyes of consumers of other or similar brands from competitors, because the higher the traffic when buying a product, the product automatically raises the brand on the internet. (Tabroni & Komarudin, 2021); (g) Helping MSME compete with large companies without having to have a large capital or place; (h) Provide wider opportunities for MSME stakeholders to implement product branding so that they are better known and have their own place in the hearts of consumers in Indonesia.

MSME actors who use digital marketing are expected to continue to learn and reflect. Be open to technology that

continues to develop. Digital marketing users must be selected by considering the right media and means to communicate the right market segmentation, so that digital marketing is more effective and not misguided (Winarti, 2021).

In addition to digital marketing, MSME actors must also pay attention to the quality of their products. The form of product quality improvement that can be done is Quality Control or QA (Quality Control), which is more detailed and ensures product hygiene and safety. Also, MSME players must adjust product and packaging resilience because they need more sales. Shelf life and product packaging are increasingly being improved (Rosmadi, 2021).

CONCLUSION

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused and affected many new problems in various areas of the economy, reducing income. MSMEs are among those affected by the decline in income. Digital marketing strategy is one of the right solutions in maintaining MSME business operations. Digital marketing can also be a great, effective strategy to increase sales of MSME players

This increase in sales can be seen from the number of effective marketing through social media and social media markets to attract the attention of consumers. MSME actors are required to use digital marketing to generate income as before the Covid-19 pandemic, which MSME actors need to master when using digital marketing, namely using social media or markets, content marketing, mobile marketing, digital marketing integration, sustainable marketing, and personalized marketing.

Therefore, a digital marketing strategy for MSME actors is one of the effective solutions that is compatible with and does not conflict with politics during the pandemic. In addition, digital marketing strategies are expected to win the competition even during the pandemic.

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